

Issues Faced By the Transgender Community Inaccessing Public Services in Khyberpakhtunkhwa

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Abstract

The Hijras are commonly ridiculed in most parts of the world due to certain misconceptions including the question of their sexual deformity. Pakistan is the home of a million Hijras mostly living below the poverty line and now commonly seeing begging at different traffic signals. The present study was designed to study the issue faced by the transgender community in accessing public services in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The study covers four districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (Swabi, Mardan, Haripur, and Mansehra) with a total sample size of 20. This qualitative study was based on interviews with transgender gurus this research covers six themes transgender population identification, public sector employment literacy, and schooling, public health, and protection. The semi-structured interview was conducted through structured questioners to gather the data from the target samples. Data were analyzed through thematic analysis by using NVIVO Software. The result show population in all four districts is mostly found uneducated presently engaged in such a profession which are not socially considered honorable. The finding also shows that they face a lot of problems while accessing public services including services in hospitals, education, less cooperation of police, totally ignored from society and also avoid by government. This research study will highlight the issues which are faced by transgender in the community.

Keywords: Transgender, Accessing Public Services

INTRODUCTION

The biology of humans indicates two major sexes, the male and female on the basis of their differences in many aspects of life. The status owned by males or females in relation to the social and cultural roles that are considered suitable for men and women is called gender. Gender identity refers to an inner sense, a self-concept of one's gender, usually female/feminine or male/masculine (Lev, 2004; Stone Fish & Harvey, 2005). Widely it is associated with tasks conception, characteristics, function, and role of males and females within the society. Everyone in society shall reflect on himself through gender identity. Therefore, gender becomes a performance through which a person can change their identity sensibly through the social process (Butler, 1990). Because of these social and structural differences women and men are equally categorized into two set at all and they need to be treated equally (Plummer, 1996; Robins et al., 1996). It is also recommended that gender operation cannot be possibly be eliminated by means of alteration of gender lifestyle (Frank & Frank, 2005).

Transgender are those who do not fall in the category of male and female (Calvin, 2016). The term transgender explains man to woman and woman to man, intersex, crossdresser, trans-sexual intersex, trans-sexual individual, and gender Queer (Clausell & Fiske, 2005). Khwaja Sara, Khusra, Murata, and Murat are different names used for transgender in Pakistan (Davidson, 2007). It is a doubtful figure that in each society especially in Pakistan this type of species is treated in undesirable ways and they are entirely ignored from their rights (Van Soest, 2018). However, the Supreme Court in 2013 ruled that Khwaja Sara has to give the same rights just to all citizens of the country (Cadena et al., 2016). The government also directed both central and provincial administrations to give them privileges in all fields of life comprising schooling, employment, and birthright (Deleu, Meire, & De Moor, 2015). Dome of the department followed the rule to consider trans-gender perform their roles in the society and this led to the nomination of 3 transgender in the election 2013 (Wilchins, 2017). According to the young adult fertility and sexuality report, there are about

11% active trans-gender in the Philippines (Nanda, 2014). The literature review showed that transgender that is considered third class are treated badly and ignored in all activities of life (Austin, 2004; Pandey, Mookerjee, & Datta, 2016). Transgender is completely overlooked in every step of life in Pakistan like administration job, education, security, health, and so many others. Although the Supreme Court of Pakistan in 2013, give them right but still it is not applied. Their families and societies are not considering them as their family members. The current study aimed to highlight the right of transgender and the main problems they are facing in society.

Many problems are faced by transgender like recognition, public sector employment, Literacy and schooling, Public health, and Protection of (Trans) life and property, and general public services. Moreover, they are facing difficulties in receiving public services from different public sector institutions like Hospitals, NADRA offices, Passport offices, etc. In the context of Pakistan, no study has been conducted properly on Transgender issues. In developed countries, Transgender will have to provide facilities as other citizens. In Pakistan, normal citizens have a lack of facilities and face issues, then how Transgender can get facilities as they are not accepted by the government and society. This research study will highlight the issues which are faced by transgender in the community. This study will also be beneficial for solving these problems. From the academic perspective, this study will also provide enough literature about transgender. The findings of this research study will leave a great impact on solving their issues.

LITRATURE REVIEW

The literature review consists of a complete definition of gender, the role of gender, definition of transgender, history of transgender, definition of the term and basic categories of transgender, transgender community in Pakistan, issues faced by the transgender community, and also of issues related to education and their health.

Gender

Individuals are recognized by birth as boys or girls, due to the appearance of their external genitalia (Bishop & Myricks, 2004). Secondary gender appearances, hormone levels, generative organs, and genes deliver extra signs concerning a person's sex. Sex distinguishes the inner sense of an individual of being boy or girl is another significant representative (Hall et al., 2008).

Gender role

Traditional gender beliefs altered significantly by the last 50 years due to changes in lifestyle, employment, demographics, the age of wedding, changes in household size, changes in household structure, and high involvement in higher education (Lueptow et al., 2001). Eagly et al., 2004) explain these phenomena in two ways i.e. descriptive and prescriptive. The descriptive phase tells people what is distinctive for their sex (Eagly, 2009). Whatever male and female typically do? The prescriptive phase of gender tells people what is good for their sex in their social framework. And whatever men and women must do?

Transgender

The individuals whose sexual characteristics at the time of birth are identified in various shapes are known as transgender (Couturier-Maillard et al., 2013; (Ellahi, Hassan & Zeeshan, 2015), or the peoples who live with intermediate gender stages are termed as transgender (Arain et al., 2016). According to Ahmedullah (2015), these are the individuals whose personal character is not confirmed and show behavior opposite to male and female. They are a unique class of knit group which contains both factors of men and women (Sharma et al., 2000). These peoples have a different social life and different gender identity from normal people. These types of people also have different emotionally as well psychologically from normal people at birth time or they may suffer from biological change later on (Fehar et al., 2017).

History of Transgender

During the Mughal period (1556 to 1857), it was reported for the first time in Hyderabad that Hijra were servants in the home of the princes and was considered as a vital advisor (Hoda, et al., 2010). They were

awarded security and many other benefits. British mortality law (1870), postponed the activities of Hijra and ignored to give them their desired rights and they were isolated from the society (CSS, forum 2010). In 2009, Dr. Aslam Khaki filed an application in the Supreme Court in reaction to a far and wide described case of police forcefulness against a group of Khawaja siras in Taxila, to be found in the Rawalpindi district of Pakistan's Punjab province. The track of the Transgender Persons (Security of Moralities) Act, 2018, is a verification of the hard work and free-for-all of the Pakistani transgender communities, as well as the upkeep and esprit de corps offered at different points by other social and civil society groups.

Islam and Transgender

The religion Islam believes in the equality law of human beings. The Islamic point of view about transgender is that they should be treated with respect, they should be praised spiritually, and they should be given shares in the properties (Khan et al., 2017). Mukhannat with male characteristics will obtain male share while Mukhannat with female characters will obtain the female share and hence Mukhannat with ambiguous characters also called Mukhannat- mushkil will obtain as the least share taken by the family member (saddi et al., 2003). Dressing rules are clearly established for males and females in Islam. The Prophet (SAW) has frustrating those males who are in resemblance of female and vice versa. The Prophet (SAW) individually did so and Caliph Umar (RAA) also did the same (Sahi Bukhari, 1986, & Sunnan-e-Ibne Maja, 1983). Prophet Muhammad (SAW) severely prohibited them by saying that it (sex) has been written in the fate of an individual and one cannot alter the intended chance by attainment castration, so there was no advantage in doing so (Sahi Bukhari, 1986). However, marriage is holy through lawful consummation, but it is not possible in the case of hermaphrodite/ intersexes. Therefore, an individual who wants to marry must notify the other about his/her impotency. If he does not do so, then he will be given punishment in Islamic law (Apkar pk, et al., 1997).

Definition of the term and basic categories

The umbrella nature of the term transgender makes it broad for diverse groups; genderqueers, cross-dressers, and transsexuals. The genderqueer discards the concept of a dual-gender scheme. Therefore, they easily blend and match the gendered actions and features related to males and females. Cross-dressers undergo moderately from minor gender physical disorders. These persons might sometimes adopt the dress of the opposed sex but otherwise existent as fellows of their birth sex. People with “tough and insistent cross-gender identification” are supposed to have a gender identity illness (American Association of psychiatry, 1994). It is not clear correctly that how Americans realize the term “transgender”. Some Americans mainly used the transsexual word for transgender in their culture (Fadlock *et al.*, 2015). It is hard to know about transgender person social policy terms due to differences in their desires and interest. According to Ahmad (2011), transgender people may have many categories such as heterosexual, homosexual, bisexual, and asexual or may ignore to labialize their sexual orientations.

Heterosexual

Those Trans genders who are sexually different like it contains both male and female sexuality (Express Tribune, 2013).

Homosexual

Those transgenders whose contain only one type of sexual behavior either female or male (Dawn, 2016).

Bisexual

Those contain bisexual behavior such as both from males or both from females (Aqsa, 2015).

Asexual

Those which contain one sexual behavior come only from male or female. Such Transgender contains only male parental or female parental behavior (Khanzada, 2016).

Accessing Public Services: Basic Understanding and types

Many public services work for transgender in order to evaluate its difficulties in which some are enlisted as, development sector professionals, Trans activists that work with the transgender community, people of the

transgender community, and public sector officials in the Islamabad region. All these communities are coordinately working for solving the problems of transgender (Ahmedullah, 2011). It has been found that the transgender class population is at risk and therefore, social workers are required to change transgender society for traditional gender change (Burdge et al., 2007). Transgender basically looking huge and ugly person, wearing bright colors and makeup (visible facial hair) with large hand and feet, nonverbal activities as well as naughty jokes, clapping, speaking rude and gesture with bloom up movements of different body parts (breast, hips) (Talwar, 1999). Basically, there are three types of Transgender

- A person who contains both genitalia is termed as Hermaphrodite.
- A person who is sterilized and becomes transgender is termed, Transsexual.
- A person who is male but female sexual character and acts like the woman is termed a Transvestites.

Transgender community in Pakistan

Numerous communities are working for the issues that arise in the way of transgender which is mentioned by (Bordia, 2014). These are the KP alliance, Baluchistan capital activist of transgender activator, Sindh social welfare department, Khwaja Sara society in Lahore, and Akhuwat Foundation are entirely working for transgender (LGBT, 2016).

Issues faced by the transgender community

There are various problems that are faced by transgender in Pakistan. These communities are working together to solve problems such as health, educational, financial, social, and other problems related to the job for them, etc. In recent Western history, transgender persons have been observed as unusual and as a byproduct of social harm. Usually, they are teased, defamed, and pathologies (Coolhart, et al., 2008). In qualitative research, it is found that transgender people are ignored in jobs, shelter, and health care (Clements, et al., 2001). This is because of no appropriate system where they proclaimed their rights. There should be a representative in assemblies that honestly represent the whole transgender community. The supreme court of Pakistan designed a law for financing them with small loans, however; the law is still waiting for implantation. In political contribution, they are demoted and not allowed to take part in elections (Ashraf et al., 2010). For instance, Republicans or more established Americans might be less ideal toward transgender rights, yet there is no unmistakable mental method of reasoning for why those impacts may reflect contemplations of body governmental issues. Incorporating increasingly mental factors into this rising examination however can make these hypothetical associations (Flores *et al.*, 2015).

There is a need for legitimate enactment on the issues of third sexual orientation network in every one of the organizations particularly inside the family, as a center of the general public. Law-making firms ought to cook the necessities of the third sexual orientation network through participatory methodology and individuals should demonstrate the dependable worry towards the nearness of the third sex individuals; consider them as a person without keeping any bias and cynicism (Jaffery *et al.*, 1996).

HIV legislation (the Prevention and Treatment Act) was drafted in 2006 and provides the framework and standards for the national response (Dickinson *et al.*, 2007). Utilizing information from an enormous scale wellbeing review, we look at the drinking examples and predominance of liquor-related issues of transgender-recognized people to non-transgender-distinguished guys and females. For transgender-distinguished individuals, we inspect how different types of exploitation identify with an overwhelming rambling of drinking (Billet et al., 2001).

Cross-sectional overviews were finished by 75,192 understudies matured 18– 29 years going to 120 post-auxiliary instructive foundations in the United States from 2011 to 2013. Self-detailed measures include liquor use, liquor-related issues, exploitation, and socioeconomics, including 3 sex character gatherings: transgender-recognized people; non-transgender distinguished guys; and non-transgender-recognized females (Kunjiapu & Yasin, 2010). Character or articulation does not fit in with the sex they were allotted during childbirth (Institute of Medicine, 2011, Gen IUSS Group *et. al.*, 2014). Cruelty incorporates harassment by outsiders on the road, verbal maltreatment, and assault with a weapon, and sexual assault (Gagne, Lombardi, *et. al.* 1996). Transgender individuals have been found to confront various troubles and

relational difficulties, for example, unveiling their sexual orientation character (Bockting and Coleman, et. al., 2016).

It was told that a total of 23% of the crime is due to sexual screening of which 15% is due to sexual abuse and 6% of them is really due to raped of sexual identity (Wittens et. al., 2003). It was also found the difference between MTFs and FTMs that in between these two 69% of the former one is suffered from raped sex while the latter suffer up to 30% due to forced sex (Kenagay *et al.*, 2005). It was suggested that Khawaja Sara's identity in the field of politics shall fail toward the cultural sources (Bernstein, et. al., 2005). Showing marginalization for transgender to ensure the existence of Khawaja Sara in politics and for this supreme court of Pakistan have submitted an article to give them rights of politics (Ahearn et al., 2001). It is recognized that Khawaja Sara is discoursed from the cultural domain due to lack of self-consciousness but due to the appearance of his unity, they don't erase the difference between citizenship (Hall *et al.*, 1997). It was also stated that Khawaja Sara is a part of the Pakistani population but has been categorically ignored and for the first time came as independently when awarded by their rights in 2009 (Herdet et. al., 2003). In Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, there were 300 attacks were reported of which 46 lead to the killing of Khawaja Sara (Mushtaq Maha, 2013). According to media reports, almost 50 Tran's people have been killed and more than 300 have faced violence and gender discrimination during the last four years in the province (Qamar Naseem, Tran's activist, 2018). The Trans community has been facing multiple challenges including harassment and kidnapping (NAYA DAUR).

Educational and health issues of transgender

The number of transgenders entertained by obtaining the data from the national database and registration authority by Kinsman (2013), indicates that the education level of transgender i.e. from primary to graduate is taken by Dr. Siama from Khwaja Sara rehabilitation program and Akhuwat Program (2015). Average results declared from the survey in California and released out an estimate for transgender population in the USA is 0.3% and the same estimate was found out for Pakistan up to 0.6% in which almost 30% of transgender people were attended school at primary level, 23% to secondary level and remaining 7% to graduate level and the later 40% did not want to go to school (Gates et al., 2011).

It is realized that face-to-face interaction with transgender can expose their problems and difficulties involving control and management (Goffman, et. al., 1969). In (2010) institute of medicine were examined issues about the health of lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender people and to identify the source of problems and their solution for this group was able to conduct research in the corresponding field. It was reported that transgender sex workers should be HIV positive. His research claims that in Karachi there was about 3.2% of male transgender has HIV positive. In addition to this united nation, the general assembly special session (2007) were reported AIDS among transgender in Pakistan ranging from 1.5 to 1.8% while in Rawalpindi this factor was reported at that time up to 2.4% respectively (Bokhari, et. al., 2007). It is also suggesting that it is needed to find out the relation between sex workers in order to measure its potential in Pakistan (Hawkes et. al., 2009). It was also evaluated that 50.8% of 360 IDUs were handover for sex in which 30.1 % of male IDUs were nominated for obtaining sex from men and women both as well as in which of the 13.4% tends to receive sex from men separately while 10% of them were reported for purchasing his sex (Haque et. al., 2004).

It was also stated that the decrease of occupational and educational opportunities has submitted Khawaja Sara in Pakistan toward continuous businesses of begging, dancing, and prostitution (Abdullah, et al 2012). Vance, Kevin recognized that education rights completely ignored transgender identity and required them to support them being a part of society (Paechter, Carrie, 2007). In a study seven transgender were interviewed in a high school, students were asked about their experiences at school. The study shows that the interviewer was complaining about nonconforming youth encounters (Wyss et al., 2004). Right off the flap needs to 'treat society'. For most trans-gendered individuals their 'sex' is changing social frames of mind, so society acknowledges that there are people who don't fit into the paired sex framework. Making the remainder of society progressively mindful of trans-gendered individuals and their shifted sex characters would be like doing work at schools and on against prejudice. This could be incorporated into training which is gone for testing sexual generalizations where all sexes can be urged to try to job or professions other than those customarily connected with their sex (Benjamin, 1954).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research approach used for conducting this study is a qualitative thematic analysis; a variant of grounded theory. This approach has a wide contribution in research to find recurring patterns, connecting with each other. Given the investigative nature of this study, the researcher originates that thematic analysis gives the elasticity to develop multiple fundamental categories in a forthright manner (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The current data which was the subject of this study was perfect for thematic analysis. There is a sufficient pool of matters to reach fullness, possibly provide deepness of understanding, and plentiful detail to expose rich considerations. In qualitative research researcher also wants to arrange interviews through structured questioners about his task from the respondent rather than to calculate data (Saunders, 20009). In the present research study, qualitative research is used in order to evaluate Issues faced by the transgender community in accessing public services in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Data Collection Method

Primary data were together by semi-structured interviews. We have arranged different interviews in different transgender places that include Mardan, Swabi, Mansehra, and Haripur. The mode of data through interviews is actually to avoid uncertainty. During interviews the normal ages of the respondent were from 20-35.

Population

The population by which the sample of semi-structured interviews was taken is the transgender of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. For this regard, the data was collected from the districts of Swabi, Mardan, Mansehra, and Haripur. The total number of transgenders residing in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa is 913 (the population of the study).

Sampling

Cooper (2008) suggested that sample is a term that is used in the research field for actually a small group of population. It is hard to take data from all populations, for this sample needed to bring accuracy. Data gathering from the large population is quite expensive and energy consumable. In order to account mentioned situations, the alternative technique convenience sampling was also used to gather information from the respondents.

Sample size

The total population of transgender is 913 in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa according to the census 2018. There are 26 districts in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Transgender are present in almost all districts of KPK except Battagram, Kohistan, Torghar, and Karak. Out of 22, the data is randomly collected from the above four districts through semi-structured interviews. The total population of transgender in these districts is 917, but the data is collected from 20 different Gurus of transgender in mentioned four districts.

Data Analysis

For analysis, we used Braun and Clarke's (2006) six stages of thematic analysis to examine the data and recognize patterns. The six steps are as follows,

1. Make clear yourself with your data.
2. Give initial code to your data to define the content
3. Hunt for themes in your codes through the different interviews
4. Evaluation patterns
5. Explain and label patterns

6. Create your report

Thematic Analysis

It is the procedure for recognizing themes in qualitative data. It is the initial qualitative methods that provide basic skills that will be helpful for conducting many other kinds of analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Especially from the point of view of learning and teaching, is that it is a method rather than a methodology (Braun & Clarke 2006; Clarke & Braun, 2013). The aim of thematic analysis is to recognize themes across the data and then use these themes to resolve the issue.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The main aim of this study was to investigate the problems confronted by the transgender community in accessing public services in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The primary goal was to find themes and subthemes that addressed the issues faced by the transgender community while accessing public services in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Conducting such study following questions were used which are given in Appendix 1. For semi-structured interview questioners were self-developed.

Q1: How do you come to this field?

This question was asked with the purpose to investigate the background reason for their presence in their current profession. We received many answers of which many reported that our family and relative's torcher we and this is the main reason to leave home and join this field. For instance, Respondent 7 told that "my father is ill....my family was facing severe financial problems and I do not have any other source of income, that's why I join this field. Respondents one said that my neighbor teases me and used harsh words to me and my family cannot support me in this matter.so I leave home and join this field. Participant 3 told us that I am not feeling comfortable and unhappy at home without transgender, so I leave home and join this field. Participants 6 and 11 said to me that the main reason for leaving home is the behavior of our relatives and family members, it is because they are torcher us and used abusive language".

From the above answer, we come to know that they have not come to this field on their wish. It is due to the behavior of their family, relatives, society, and a few financial problems that force them to come into this field.

Q2: what are the problems which you are facing in the society?

Some of the participants responded that people use abusive language to us and they also torture us physically as well as mentally. While some other respondents said that when we come out of our Daras (their residence) people around us have had bad eyes, using abusive language and also shouting at us. For instance, participants 15 and 20 responded that when we come out of our places people tease us. They are laughing and using abusive language to us. Participants 9 and 17 said that when we go to Bazar people have bad eyes on us, and they also shout at us. Participants 1 and 13 told that when we come out of our living places people torcher us physically as well as mentally.

From the above answers, it is evident that they live a hard life in society. On every step, they face hurdles from society in the form of physical and mental torchers and abusive language. Living in society is very difficult for him.

Q3: Do you like this profession with all your heart?

Most of the participants responded that we do not like this work from heart, but we don't have any other skills and profession or any other source of income for a livelihood, that's why we cannot leave this profession. Two of the participants said that we are fully satisfied in this profession and we don't like to do any other job. Participants 6, 9, and 13 told us that we do not like this profession from heart, but we have no other source of income and not any other skills that we used and earn money for our living.

From the above paragraph, it is clear that the majority of the transgender do not like this field from the heart, but due to the lack of skills and profession and no other source of income, they come to this field.

Q4: Do you want to leave this field and join another work?

This question was asked from the informants to know their willingness to leave this field and joined other fields of interest. The majority of the respondent told that they want to leave this profession if the government provides other opportunities. We want to join the field of dress designing, beauty parlor, tailoring, and cooking. For example, one participant said that I do not learn any skills, nor did I want to leave this profession. Participants 2, 8, and 12 said that *they* want to learn the skills of beauty parlor and tailoring if anyone provides him such an opportunity. Participants 3, 7, and 14 told us that *we want* to learn the skills of cooking and boutique.

From the above answer, it is clear that they are unhappy and uncomfortable in this field and want to learn other skills if government or NGO's provide them any opportunities. They want to learn skills of the beauty parlor, tailoring, cooking, and boutique.

Q5: Do you have any skills?

With the intention of knowing their hidden skills, this question was asked from the participants of the study. Some of them told that we know the work of tailoring and cooking. Some told that we know the work of beauty parlor and boutique. One of them told that I know driving. Two of them said that we have no skills. For instance, participants 10, 13, and 20 told us that we have skills in cooking, tailoring, and boutique. Participants 1, 7, and 11 said that we have skills in a beauty parlor. Participant 19 told that I have skills of driving and could earn money for my livelihood if the opportunity provided.

From the above, it is concluded that they have some good skills but due to no support of society and government and lack of resources, they can't use their skills.

Q6: Do you want to learn/develop any skills?

The majority of the responses come in yes. Some responded told that they want to learn the skills of boutiques and tailoring. Some participants said that we want to learn skills of cooking and also dress designing. Some of them told that as we already have skills of tailoring, cooking and beauty parlor, so we want to improve these skills. For example, two of them told that we want to learn the skills of the beauty parlor. Three of them told that we want to learn the skills of tailoring and dress designing. Four of them said that we want to learn the skills of the boutique. Two participants said that they want to learn skills of cooking. Three participants told that they want to learn skills of driving. One participant said that I do not want to learn any skills. Four of them told that we want to improve our existing skills.

From the above answers, it is clear that they want to learn and improve their skills and leave their current field if provided an opportunity to them freely.

Q7: Which type of problems are you facing in NADRA and hospitals?

All of the respondents are very happy and fully satisfied with NADRA because it issued NICS to him without any problem. On the other hand, all of them are dissatisfied with the hospital's services. We face many problems as we are going to hospitals. We are unsatisfied with the services of doctors and rude behaviors of people present at hospitals and also from the hospital peon. They told that we face hurdles and problems at the hospital. For instance, from the hospital's point of view 5 of them told that peoples laugh at us when they see us in hospitals. 10 of them told that Peon hardly gives us numbers and the doctor does not check well like they check other people. Five of them said that when we go to the hospital people have bad eyes on us, make dirty jokes, and also tease us.

From this, we concluded that they are fully satisfied with NADRA services but totally dissatisfied with the services of hospitals and also from the presence of people who are in hospitals.

Q8: Are your life and property are safe?

All of the respondents said that their life and property are not safe in society. It is because of the behavior of the society and also very little support from the police. For example, 10 participants told that when we return from function people on the way beat us and snatch our money from us and also sometimes rape us. Eight of them told us that some people come to our Daras (residence) at night, they beat us and snatch away the money from us and sometimes rape us. Two of the participants said that our life and property are safe, and we don't have any problems. The life of a transgender is dependent on the mercy of society. It is very hard for him to live a peaceful life without the support of society.

Q9: Beside the aforementioned, what are the problems that you are facing in society?

This question was asked to know the problems other than a mention in the answer of question NO two. They face other problems as living in the society. For example, participants 2, 5, 11, and 13 told us that people do not give us houses on rent, and if they even provide us a house on rent, they charge double rent as normal. Participants 1, 9, 15, and 20 told that when we take a house on rent, the owner, without showing the electricity and gas bill and take away more bill as of original. One participant said that I have no problem with the owner of the house and I got a house easily on rent.

From the above paragraph, it is clear they have also a problem in taking a house for rent. If they even got a house on rent the owner of the house charges more rent as normally provided to other people. The owner also charges heavy bills without showing the bill.

Discussion

By using thematic analysis, we concluded that transgender does not come to this field on their own wish. It is due to the behavior of their family, relatives, society, and financial problem that forces them to join this field. On every step, they face hurdles from society in the form of mental and physical torture and abusive language. It is also noted that they are unhappy and uncomfortable in this field and want to learn other skills if government and NGO's provide them any opportunities. After conducting interviews, the researcher also knows that they have good skills but due to no support from society, government, and lack of resources they can't use their skills. If society provided them an opportunity to leave freely then they are able to learn new skills. It is also concluded that they are fully satisfied with NADRA services but totally dissatisfied with the services of hospitals. It is also noted that the life of a transgender is totally dependent on the mercy of society. It is very hard for them to live a peaceful life without the support of society. After conducting interviews with transgender, it is also concluded that they are facing problems by taking a house for rent. If they even got a house on rent the owner of the house charges more rents as normally provided to other people. The owner also charges heavy bills without showing the bills.

Theoretical Aspect

Initially, this work contributes to theory by awarding directions to demonstrate the issues faced by the transgender community in accessing public services in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Such types of research were also done previously on the rights of transgender at various aspects.

Secondly, this research also encourages the solution of the concerned problems in order to award transgender people through valid strategies to give them their rights. This research involves important support toward the issues faced by the transgender community in accessing public services from literature in a good deal.

Findings

This research study collapses on four sides of the transgender problems mainly included HIV, AIDS, and also include education issues. The given study shows some strange problems faced by transgender society and restrictions in their public services. No literature was previously nominated on the current topic titled as issues faced by the transgender community in accessing public services in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Our study results support the previous research done by the AAWAZ program (2016), funded by the UK Aid and by research scholar Intikhab Ahmad et al., (2017) on the issues faced by the Transgender community.

Limitations and Future Direction of the Study

This research study also resides some limitations future direction which are given as under.

- First sample size is limited to 20.
- The research area is only limited to KPK.
- Research interviews were only concerned with the transgender community only
- This research study is only limited to a few regions of KPK.
- Further research study should be constructed in other cities of Pakistan.
- For further research it is also needed to find out the solution to the problems faced by the transgender community while assessing public services.
- Future research work will be concerned on this topic in other regions included public sectors as well as government sectors too.
- Interview could be taken from other people not only from transgender for future work.
- Quantitative research techniques could be utilized for future research. .

IMPLICATION FOR GOVERNMENTAL

- Government must take action to legalize the separate identity of the Hijra community and give strict orders to implement in public machinery.
- The media should play a responsible role for the Hijra community to protect their rights and identities.
- Government should also direct the religious scholars to play a sensible role and also educate the general public to treat the Hijra community with dignity and respect.
- Government should decide to announce a job quota for the Hijra community.
- Public service messages should promote for bringing Hijra into the overall economic market of the country.
- Government should maintain and facilitate the whole record of the Transgender Community on the district level, so that they may be provided adequate financial support to protect them from involving an unethical activity in society.

Conclusion

The main goal of the study work is to discover the transgender problem which is titled in the thesis as issues faced by the transgender community in accessing public services in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Analysis shows that the transgender community is widely affected by many problems included health problems, education, and other common problems related to them.

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